
Interplay of Clusters of Acoustic and Intrinsic Thermoacoustic Modes in Can-Annular Combustors

Guillaume J. J. Fournier*

Technical University of Munich
TUM School of Engineering and Design
Department of Engineering Physics and Computation
Boltzmannstr. 15
85748 Garching, Germany
e-mail: fournier@tfd.mw.tum.de

Felicitas Schaefer

Technical University of Munich
TUM School of Engineering and Design
Department of Engineering Physics and Computation
Boltzmannstr. 15
85748 Garching, Germany
e-mail: schaefer@tfd.mw.tum.de

Matthias Haeringer

Technical University of Munich
TUM School of Engineering and Design
Department of Engineering Physics and Computation
Boltzmannstr. 15
85748 Garching, Germany
e-mail: haeringer@tfd.mw.tum.de

Camilo F. Silva

Technical University of Munich
TUM School of Engineering and Design
Department of Engineering Physics and Computation
Boltzmannstr. 15
85748 Garching, Germany
e-mail: silva@tfd.mw.tum.de

Wolfgang Polifke

Technical University of Munich
TUM School of Engineering and Design
Department of Engineering Physics and Computation
Boltzmannstr. 15
85748 Garching, Germany
e-mail: polifke@tum.de

* Address all correspondence to this author.

ABSTRACT

Thermoacoustic systems can exhibit self-excited instabilities of two nature, namely cavity modes or intrinsic thermoacoustic (ITA) modes. In heavy-duty land-based gas turbines with can-annular combustors, the cross-talk between cans causes the cavity modes of various azimuthal order to create clusters, i.e. ensembles of modes with close frequencies. Similarly, in systems exhibiting rotational symmetry, ITA modes also have the peculiar behavior of forming clusters. In the present study, we investigate how such clusters interplay when they are located in the same frequency range. We first consider a simple Rijke tube configuration and derive a general analytical low-order network model using only dimensionless numbers. We investigate the trajectories of the eigenmodes when changing the downstream length and the flame position. In particular, we show that ITA and acoustic modes can switch nature and their trajectories are strongly influenced by the presence of exceptional points. We then study a generic can-annular combustor. We show that such configuration can be approximated by an equivalent Rijke tube. We demonstrate that, in the absence of mean flow, the eigenvalues of the system necessarily lie on specific trajectories imposed by the upstream conditions.

NOMENCLATURE

Roman

c_u, c_d [m s⁻¹] Speed of sound upstream/downstream

f, g [m s⁻¹] Characteristic waves amplitudes

\mathcal{F} [-] Flame transfer function

H [m] Width of a can

L_u, L_d [m] Length of the upstream/downstream duct

L_g [m] Size of the gap

L_g^* [-] Coupling strength, $L_g^* = L_g/H$

\mathcal{L}_m [m] Equivalent length

m [-] Bloch wave number

n [-] Interaction index of the flame

N [-] Number of cans

p' [Pa] Acoustic pressure

\dot{q}' [-] Normalized heat release fluctuations

R_i, R_o [-] Reflection coefficient at the inlet/outlet

\mathcal{R}_m [-] Equivalent reflection coefficient

s [rad s⁻¹] Laplace variable, $s = \sigma + i\omega$

s^* [-] Dimensionless Laplace variable, $s^* = s\tau_F$

St [-] Strouhal number, $St = \nu\tau_F$

T_u, T_d [K] Upstream/downstream temperature

u' [m s⁻¹] Acoustic velocity

Greek

θ [-] Normalized temperature ratio, $\theta = T_d/T_u - 1$

ν [Hz] Frequency

ξ [-] Ratio of specific impedances, $\xi = \bar{\rho}_u c_u / \bar{\rho}_d c_d$

$\bar{\rho}_u, \bar{\rho}_d$ [kg m⁻³] Upstream/downstream mean density

σ [s⁻¹] Growth rate

τ_F [s] Time delay of the flame

τ_u, τ_d [s] Upstream/downstream propagation time, $\tau_i = L_i/c_i$

τ_u^*, τ_d^* [-] Dimensionless upstream/downstream propagation time, $\tau_i^* = \tau_i/\tau_F$

τ_m^* [-] Dimensionless equivalent propagation time

τ_t^* [-] Total dimensionless propagation time, $\tau_t^* = \tau_d^* + \tau_m^*$

ω [rad s⁻¹] Angular frequency, $\omega = 2\pi\nu$

Abbreviations

FTF Flame transfer function

XP Exceptional point

1 INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Lean premixed combustion systems have been developed in order to reduce emissions and address environmental issues. Unfortunately, such technology is also more prone to combustion instabilities [1, 2]. The coupling between the unsteady heat release of the flame and the acoustics of the system may result in a positive feedback loop leading to self-excited instabilities with growing pressure fluctuations. It is crucial to understand and mitigate such phenomenon as repeated exposure to high level of pressure can lead to catastrophic engine failure [3].

Since the Apollo program and the development of modern rocket engines, thermoacoustic instabilities have been interpreted as acoustic eigenmodes of the system driven by unsteady heat release [4, 5]. However, Hoeijmakers et al. [6, 7], experimentally and with a simple analytical model, showed evidence of thermoacoustic instabilities in an anechoic environment. This situation was paradoxical and constituted a significant deviation from the established

interpretation. These observations were later confirmed with high-fidelity numerical simulations [8,9]. Bomberg et al. [10] formally identified the so-called ITA feedback loop, a flame-flow-acoustic interaction intrinsic to the flame and its immediate surrounding and not involving the acoustics of the system, which allowed Emmert et al. [11] to justify the physical nature of the previous observations. Emmert et al. [12] then demonstrated that the ITA feedback loop gives rise to a new set of thermoacoustic modes of different nature also for reflecting boundaries and identified such an ITA mode as the most unstable mode in a longitudinal test-rig. Yong et al. [13] showed that for a marginally stable ITA mode, the velocity fluctuations and the gradient of pressure fluctuations change sign across the flame, thus providing a simple identification criterion.

This new paradigm fundamentally changed the understanding of thermoacoustic instabilities and shed a new light on inexplicable phenomena reported in earlier studies, such as “the new set of modes” described by Dowling and Stow [14], the “bulk mode” highlighted by Eckstein and Sattelmayer [15, 16], or the “convective scaling” of thermoacoustic eigenfrequencies [17]. Numerous studies then investigated the role of both types of thermoacoustic instabilities. Hosseini et al. investigated the interplay between modes of ITA and acoustic origin and showed that, when they are far away from one another, they do not influence each other [18]. Mensah et al. [19] highlighted the presence of exceptional points in the spectrum due to the coalescence of modes of ITA and acoustic origin. Silva et al. [20] and Orchini et al. [21] further investigated the role of exceptional points in the interplay between ITA and acoustic modes and highlighted characteristic trajectories. Buschmann et al. [22, 23] observed the existence of ITA modes in an annular combustor and showed that they appear in clusters, i.e. a collection of eigenmodes with close oscillation frequencies but different growth rates. Fournier et al. [24] used a low-order model to explain why the ITA clusters align around a “pure ITA frequency”, i.e. the frequency of an ITA mode in an anechoic environment.

Annular and can-annular combustors exhibit discrete rotational symmetry and the azimuthal dimension leads to interesting new properties. Numerical simulations [25, 26] and experiments [27] revealed that the full can-annular configuration gives rise to new eigenmodes, with mode shapes involving multiple cans, that do not exist in a single can approximation. Farisco et al. [28] numerically investigated the effect of the gap, demonstrated that the cross-talk between cans cannot be ignored and estimated a transmission coefficient. Ghirardo et al. [29] gave further proof using two-dimensional (2D) Helmholtz simulations and experimental results. They highlighted that modes of various azimuthal orders emerge due to the weak coupling between cans and form clusters of acoustic modes. Jegal et al. [30] and Moon et al. [31, 32] used a test-rig with two and four cans, respectively, to explore the effect of can coupling on the stability of the burners. Because the eigenmodes are closely spaced in clusters, mixed states, with several distinct types of interaction patterns, were observed.

Recent studies tackled the problem at a more fundamental level using low-order network models. Fournier et

Fig. 1: Spectrum of two generic can-annular combustors obtained with FEM computations. Parameters are given in Table 1. For Configuration A (blue circles), the ITA and acoustic clusters are distinct and identifiable. Two modes are offset from their respective clusters, which is explained later in the paper. In Configuration B (orange diamonds), the flame position inside the combustor is changed but the total length is kept constant. The clusters become entangled and cannot be distinguished from one another.

al. [24] proposed the modeling of the gap as a thin annulus and the method was applied by Haeringer et al. [33] in a strategy to tune single-can test-rigs to mimic full engines. Von Saldern et al. [34] proposed to model the cross-talk between cans with the Rayleigh conductivity, which relates the acoustic flux through the aperture to the pressure gradient between cans. Both modeling approaches were compared by Fournier et al. [35] and an extension was given, using a flow parameter in terms of a characteristic length, giving quantitatively accurate results. Von Saldern et al. [36] derived an effective impedance model for non-compact connections and analyzed the role of liners in damping azimuthal thermoacoustic modes. Orchini [37] and Pedergnana and Noiray [38] explored the effect of mean flow and derived effective impedance models that show explicit dependence on the grazing flow Mach number. Orchini et al. [39] then showed that such effect gives rise to new sets of clusters of modes of aeroacoustic origin due to the coupling with the response of the shear layer in the apertures.

Both phenomena of ITA clusters in annular configuration and acoustic clusters in can-annular configurations are fairly well understood taken individually. In the present study, we want to investigate the interplay between clusters of acoustic and ITA modes in a can-annular combustor when they are located in the same frequency range. The motivation of our study is illustrated by Fig. 1, which shows the spectrum of two generic can-annular combustors obtained with FEM Helmholtz computations using COMSOL MULTIPHYSICS. The geometrical and thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 1 and both configurations are investigated more in depth in Sec. 4. For Configuration A,

Fig. 2: Schematic of a generic Rijke tube of length L_u upstream the flame, L_d downstream the flame. The acoustic boundaries are defined by the reflection coefficients R_i and R_o at the inlet and outlet respectively.

the ITA and acoustic clusters are distinct and identifiable. In Configuration B, the flame position differs by only 15% but the total length of the combustor is kept constant. In this scenario, the clusters cannot be distinguished from one another and seem to be entangled. The paper aims at explaining such drastic change in the spectrum and giving more insight on the ITA and acoustic trajectories in can-annular combustors.

Fournier et al. [24] and Haeringer et al. [33] showed that, under some assumptions discussed later in the paper, a can-annular combustor can be fairly well represented by an equivalent Rijke tube. The latter is one of the simplest thermoacoustic system and has been extensively studied for decades. This allows us to gain insight at a more fundamental level. Therefore, the paper structures as follows: in Sec. 2, we first consider a simple Rijke tube and analytically derive the dispersion relation. The problem remains generally applicable to configurations of arbitrary geometrical and thermodynamic parameters thanks to the use of Buckingham II theorem and dimensionless numbers. In Sec. 3, we then investigate the influence of the length of the Rijke tube and the flame position inside it on both ITA and acoustic modes. In Sec. 4, the results are transposed to two generic can-annular combustors and allow us to explain the spectrum observed in Fig. 1. Finally, the modeling assumptions and the limits of validity are discussed.

2 NETWORK MODEL OF A GENERIC RIJKE TUBE CONFIGURATION

2.1 Case and Flow Description

The system considered is a generic Rijke tube, as depicted in Fig. 2. Ducts of length L_u and L_d are placed upstream and downstream of the flame respectively. The acoustic boundaries are defined by the reflection coefficients R_i and R_o at the inlet and outlet, respectively. We assume zero mean flow when modeling the thermoacoustic behavior of the system, in particular wave propagation in the ducts. The model is based on a network approach. Recall the definition of the characteristic waves amplitudes:

$$f \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{p'}{\bar{\rho}c} + u' \right), \quad g \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{p'}{\bar{\rho}c} - u' \right) \quad (1)$$

In the ducts, we assume that only 1D planar acoustic waves propagate. The f and g waves in the system relate as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_u \\ g_u \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-s\tau_u} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{s\tau_u} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_i \\ g_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} f_o \\ g_o \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-s\tau_d} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{s\tau_d} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_d \\ g_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The term $e^{\pm s\tau}$ represents the phase change resulting from the acoustic propagation of the wave and τ is the time it takes to travel. $\tau_u = L_u/c_u$ and $\tau_d = L_d/c_d$ are the propagation times upstream and downstream the flame respectively, c_u and c_d are the speed of sound in the respective regions, and $s = \sigma + i\omega$ is the Laplace variable, with σ the growth rate and ω the angular frequency.

The acoustic boundary conditions of the system are defined using reflection coefficients. The latter write as follows:

$$R_i = \frac{f_i}{g_i}, \quad R_o = \frac{g_o}{f_o} \quad (3)$$

2.2 Flame and Unsteady Heat Release Model

The acoustic flame model is derived using the linearized Rankine Hugoniot jump equations for a compact heat source at rest with unsteady heat release fluctuations [11, 40].

$$\begin{cases} \frac{p'_d}{\bar{\rho}_d c_d} = \xi \frac{p'_u}{\bar{\rho}_u c_u} \\ u'_d = u'_u + \theta \dot{q}' \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $\xi = \bar{\rho}_u c_u / \bar{\rho}_d c_d$ is the ratio of specific impedances, $\theta = (T_d - T_u) / T_u$ the normalized temperature ratio and $\dot{q}' = \dot{Q}' \bar{u}_u / \bar{Q}$ the normalized global heat release fluctuations of the flame.

A Flame Transfer Function (FTF) is used to relate the unsteady heat release fluctuations \dot{q}' to the acoustic velocity fluctuations upstream the flame u'_u . For this study, the famous $n - \tau$ model from Crocco is used [41].

$$\frac{\dot{q}'}{u'_u} = \mathcal{F}(s) = n e^{-s\tau_F} \quad (5)$$

with n and τ_F the gain and time delay of the flame respectively. Such a simple model captures the essential aspects of a generic flame and is convenient to use in the context of low-order models as it allows to derive analytical solutions.

Writing Eq. (4) with the characteristic waves amplitudes f and g and inserting Eq. (5) leads to the flame transfer matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_d \\ g_d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{T}_a(s) & \mathcal{T}_b(s) \\ \mathcal{T}_b(s) & \mathcal{T}_a(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_u \\ g_u \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The matrix is symmetric, with $\mathcal{T}_a(s) = \frac{1}{2}(\xi + 1 + n\theta e^{-s\tau_F})$ and $\mathcal{T}_b(s) = \frac{1}{2}(\xi - 1 - n\theta e^{-s\tau_F})$.

2.3 Dimensionless Non-Linear Eigenvalue Problem

Combining Eqs. (2, 3, 6), the governing equations of the system can be cast in the matrix form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -R_i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -R_o & 1 \\ \mathcal{T}_a(s)e^{-s(\tau_u+\tau_d)} & \mathcal{T}_b(s)e^{s(\tau_u-\tau_d)} & -1 & 0 \\ \mathcal{T}_b(s)e^{-s(\tau_u-\tau_d)} & \mathcal{T}_a(s)e^{s(\tau_u+\tau_d)} & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_i \\ g_i \\ f_o \\ g_o \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The four governing equations describing the system involve the following parameters: the Laplace variable s , the propagation times τ_u and τ_d , the ratio of specific impedances ξ , the temperature ratio θ , the reflection coefficients R_i and R_o , the time delay of the flame τ_F and its gain n . Among these nine parameters, five are already dimensionless: n , ξ , θ , R_i and R_o . The remaining four parameters admit a basis of one fundamental dimension, time. Applying Buckingham II theorem [42,43], we define the following dimensionless numbers:

$$s^* = s\tau_F, \quad \tau_u^* = \frac{\tau_u}{\tau_F}, \quad \tau_d^* = \frac{\tau_d}{\tau_F} \quad (8)$$

The system is therefore fully described using eight independent dimensionless numbers. The non-dimensionalization of the problem allows us to generalize the results to configurations of arbitrary geometrical and thermodynamic parameters, and therefore allows us to draw general conclusions. This approach has successfully been applied in ther-

moacoustics [29, 35, 43].

Mathematically, Eq. (7) has non-trivial solutions if the determinant of the matrix is null. Solving for the determinant and using the dimensionless numbers defined in Eq. (8) leads to the dispersion relation:

$$\mathcal{D}(s^*) = \left(\xi + 1 + n\theta e^{-s^*} \right) \left(1 - R_i R_o e^{-2s^*(\tau_u^* + \tau_d^*)} \right) + \left(\xi - 1 - n\theta e^{-s^*} \right) \left(R_i e^{-2s^* \tau_u^*} - R_o e^{-2s^* \tau_d^*} \right) = 0 \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) is non-linear in s^* and can generally not be solved analytically. Instead, we solve it numerically using taX¹, the open-source Matlab package developed by the TFD group to build and solve low-order thermoacoustic network models [44]. taX transforms Eq. (9) into a linear eigenvalue problem, thus facilitating the use of direct solvers to easily find all eigenmodes, in particular ITA modes, which remain difficult to find with iterative methods due to their small basin of attraction [22, 45].

2.4 Interesting Special Cases

Although Eq. (9) is non-linear in s^* , in some cases, it can be solved analytically. We discuss here three interesting limit cases. In the following, we assume the reflection coefficients R_i and R_o to be real-valued and independent of frequency.

- For the case of a very weak flame (i.e. $n \approx 0$), the dispersion relation reduces to $1 - R_i R_o e^{-2s^*(\tau_u^* + \tau_d^*)} = 0$ and we recover the classical solution for an acoustic mode in a duct [7, 46].

$$\begin{cases} St = \nu\tau_F = \frac{j}{4(\tau_u^* + \tau_d^*)} \\ \sigma\tau_F = \frac{1}{2(\tau_u^* + \tau_d^*)} \ln \left(R_i R_o (-1)^j \right) \end{cases}, \quad j \in \mathbb{N} \quad (10)$$

where the Strouhal number St is the dimensionless frequency.

- In the case of anechoic boundaries $R_i = R_o = 0$, Eq. (9) becomes $\xi + 1 + n\theta e^{-s^*} = 0$. The acoustic modes disappear and only the pure ITA modes remain, i.e. ITA modes in an anechoic environment. This was extensively

¹<https://gitlab.lrz.de/tfd/tax>

discussed in previous studies [7, 11] and the eigenfrequencies are given by:

$$\begin{cases} St = \nu\tau_F = \frac{(2j+1)}{2} \\ \sigma\tau_F = \ln\left(\frac{n\theta}{1+\xi}\right) \end{cases}, \quad j \in \mathbb{N} \quad (11)$$

- A third remarkable case arises when the boundaries are identical $R_i = R_o$, and when the flame is placed in the Rijke tube specifically such as the propagation times in the upstream and downstream ducts are identical $\tau_u^* = \tau_d^*$. In this configuration, the dispersion relation becomes:

$$\left(\xi + 1 + n\theta e^{-s^*}\right) \left(1 - R_i R_o e^{-2s^*(\tau_u^* + \tau_d^*)}\right) = 0 \quad (12)$$

The dispersion relation is factored in two terms. The first term corresponds to the dispersion relation in an anechoic environment, leading to pure ITA modes, the second term is the dispersion relation for a pure acoustic system. Although a flame is present and the acoustic boundaries are not anechoic, the eigenvalues of the thermoacoustic system correspond exactly to the pure ITA and acoustic modes defined by Eqs. (10, 11). Such a result can be explained using phasor analysis, which has already been used in thermoacoustics [13, 16, 17, 24, 47–49]. For example, if we consider the case of fully reflecting boundaries $R_i = R_o = \pm 1$, the acoustic mode is marginally stable, thus simplifying the phasor analysis with arrows of fixed length. At the inlet and the outlet, to satisfy the boundary conditions, the phasor f and g have opposite directions (case Open-Open) or same directions (case Closed-Closed) respectively. Traveling from the boundaries to the flame, from both upstream and downstream sides, the phasors rotate by an identical angle $\omega\tau_u = \omega\tau_d = \pi/2$. The flame is located at a velocity node or a pressure node, respectively. The eigenmodes are simply the half-wave modes for a simple acoustic system with a temperature jump.

3 INTERPLAY OF ITA AND ACOUSTIC EIGENMODES

In this section, we investigate the impact on the eigenmodes of the length of the Rijke tube and the position of the flame inside it. We consider here only the case Open-Open $R_i = R_o = -1$. The FTF parameters n and τ_F are kept constant, as well as the flame thermodynamic parameters θ , ξ .

Fig. 3: Trajectories of the eigenmodes in the complex plane for a short upstream, $\tau_u^* = 0.1$ fixed. When increasing τ_d^* , i.e. increasing the downstream length, as expected, the frequency of the acoustic mode decreases. On the other hand, the ITA is around its pure ITA frequency $St = 1/2$ but its growth rate changes. Eventually, the ITA mode converges to the semi-anechoic configuration identified by the cross. The circle indicates when $\tau_d^* = \tau_u^*$, i.e. when the modes are fully decoupled according to Eq. (12). However, note that the acoustic mode is outside of the frequency range of interest and therefore not visible.

3.1 Short Upstream Length

In this case, we consider a short upstream length, the dimensionless upstream propagation time is small $\tau_u^* = 0.1$. We change the downstream length, i.e. we vary the downstream dimensionless propagation time τ_d^* from 0 to 2, all other parameters being held constant. We consider only the fundamental acoustic and ITA thermoacoustic modes and disregard all the higher-order modes.

Figure 3 depicts the trajectories in the complex plane of both eigenmodes. When increasing the downstream length, the frequency of the acoustic mode decreases, as expected. For the ITA mode, when τ_d^* is small, the acoustic mode is far away and the two modes do not interplay. Therefore, its growth rate changes but the frequency remains constant and equal to the pure ITA frequency $St = \nu\tau_F = 1/2$ [20, 21, 50]. When increasing τ_d^* , the ITA mode eventually converges to a special point, indicated by the cross in Fig. 3. The point can clearly be identified: the system behaves exactly as if, just after the flame, the duct L_d and the outlet boundary are replaced by a non-reflecting boundary, i.e. $R = 0$, while the upstream condition remains unchanged ($R_i = -1$). The flame is placed in an effective semi-anechoic environment. This can be explained by the fact that $R_d = g_d/f_d = R_o e^{-2s^* \tau_d^*}$, and for positive growth rate, when τ_d^* increases, $\lim_{\tau_d \rightarrow \infty} |R_d| = |R_o| e^{-\sigma \tau_d} \approx 0$. In other words, the longer the downstream duct, the weaker the effective reflection coefficient for an unstable mode. The system downstream the flame is equivalent to a

Fig. 4: Trajectories of the eigenmodes in the complex plane for a longer upstream length $\tau_u^* = 0.2$ fixed. For small values of τ_d^* , the ITA mode has once more its frequency near the pure ITA frequency $St = 1/2$ and its growth rate increases with τ_d^* . However, the ITA mode does not converge to the semi-anechoic point, identified by the cross, but passes around it while its frequency keeps decreasing. Conversely, the acoustic mode first decrease in frequency but then converges to the semi-anechoic eigenmode. The two eigenmodes switch nature. The circle indicates when $\tau_d^* = \tau_u^*$ and the ITA mode is solution of Eq. (11).

non-reflecting boundary.

The red circles mark the setup where $\tau_d^* = \tau_u^*$. For this specific scenario, the two modes are decoupled as shown by Eq. (12). Here, the acoustic mode is outside of the frequency range of interest and therefore not shown on Fig. 3. However, the ITA mode is indeed present and verifies the analytical expression Eq. (11).

Figure 4 shows similar results for a different upstream configuration. In this case, the upstream length is such that $\tau_u^* = 0.2$, and all other parameters are kept constant and identical to the previous case. We vary the downstream length, i.e. τ_d^* increases from 0 to 2. Similarly to the previous case, when τ_d^* remains small, the ITA and acoustic modes are far away from each other and do not interplay: the ITA mode has a constant pure ITA frequency $St = 1/2$ and its growth rate changes. However, for larger downstream lengths, the ITA mode does not converge to the semi-anechoic mode, but passes around it and keeps decreasing in frequency: it turns into the acoustic mode. Conversely, the mode initially classified as acoustic, when τ_d^* is small, first decreases in frequency but then converges to the semi-anechoic eigenmode. It is highlighted that the two modes can switch nature, as previously reported [18, 34, 46]. However, we will not discuss how the eigenmodes can be classified as ITA and acoustic and when precisely the modes switch nature as this question is out of the scope of this study and already discussed by Yong et al. [49].

Fig. 5: Trajectories of the eigenmodes for the upstream configuration $\tau_u^* = 0.45$. When increasing τ_d^* , the modes first converge towards each other before changing direction, suggesting the presence of an exceptional point. The circles indicate when $\tau_d^* = \tau_u^*$, the acoustic and ITA modes are effectively decoupled and are solutions of Eqs. (10, 11). Similarly to the results shown in Fig. 4, the eigenmodes also switch nature.

3.2 Long Upstream Length: The Impact of an Exceptional Point on the Acoustic and ITA Trajectories

We now investigate the trajectories when the dimensionless upstream propagation time is large $\tau_u^* = 0.45$. All other parameters are kept constant and equal to the case described in Sec. 3.1. The downstream length is again varied such that τ_d^* increases from 0 to 2. Figure 5 shows the trajectories of the eigenmodes in the complex plane. When increasing τ_d^* , the two eigenmodes first converge towards each other before changing directions, which suggests the presence of an exceptional point (XP) in the vicinity in the parameter space. The circles indicate when the propagation times are identical $\tau_d^* = \tau_u^*$; the eigenmodes satisfy the pure ITA and acoustic modes defined by Eqs. (10, 11).

Exceptional points are found in various disciplines, including thermoacoustics [19, 20]. At an exceptional point, at least two eigenvalues and their respective eigenfunctions coalesce, and the eigenvalue sensitivity with respect to changes in parameters becomes infinite. Recall that the eigenvalues are the solution of the dispersion relation:

$$\mathcal{D}(s^*; \tau_d^*, n) = 0 \quad (9)$$

Eigenvalues can be classified according to their algebraic and geometric multiplicity, am and gm respectively. The algebraic multiplicity quantifies the multiplicity of the eigenvalue as a root of the dispersion relation Eq. (9). The

Fig. 6: Identification of an exceptional point for the upstream case $\tau_u^* = 0.45$. Colors indicate isolines of flame strength n . When varying the dimensionless downstream propagation time τ_d^* from 0.42 to 0.48, the XP causes the eigenmodes to strongly veer, leading to the characteristic trajectories observed in Fig. 5.

geometric multiplicity is the dimension of the associated eigenspace, i.e. the number of linearly independent eigenvectors. Eigenvalues can be simple ($am = gm = 1$), semi-simple ($am = gm > 1$) or defective ($am > gm$). Defective eigenvalues that are branch-point singularities are called exceptional points (XPs). In the context of thermoacoustics, XPs are primarily attributed to the interplay between intrinsic thermoacoustic modes (ITA) and acoustic modes, i.e. thermoacoustic modes of different nature [19]. Previous studies have investigated XPs associated to the parameters (n, τ_F) [19,43], or (τ_c, R_o) , where τ_c is the time-delay of a realistic flame impulse response [51]. Indeed, for the modes to coalesce, they need to have the same frequency, mainly driven by τ_F or τ_c for an ITA mode, and the same growth rate, mainly driven by the gain (strength of the flame n) or losses ($R_o \neq \pm 1$).

In the present study, the approach is different because the time-delay of the flame τ_F is fixed, which in turn settles the value of the pure ITA frequency (solution of Eq. (11)). By changing τ_d^* , we allow the acoustic mode to move in the complex plane and be in the same frequency range as the ITA mode. For the modes to coalesce, their growth rates must also be equal, which is obtained by changing the strength of the flame n . According to Mensah et al. [19], for an ITA and acoustic mode to coalesce, the following relations need to be satisfied:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \mathcal{D}(s^*; \tau_d^*, n)}{\partial s^*} = 0 & (13) \\ \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{D}(s^*; \tau_d^*, n)}{\partial s^{*2}} \neq 0 & (14) \end{cases}$$

Fig. 7: Unit-cell of a generic can-annular combustor. The flame is placed at a distance L_u and L_d from the inlet and the outlet, respectively. The can is decoupled from the plenum at the inlet and closed at the outlet. However, acoustic communication with the neighboring cans is possible through the gap L_g . Parameters are given in Table 1.

The solution of the complex-valued Eqs. (9, 13) is the set of parameters (τ_d^*, n_{XP}) and the defective eigenvalue s_{XP}^* . We highlight here one special configuration where an easy analytical solution is found. For the special case where $\tau_d^* = \tau_u^* = 1/2$, following Eqs. (10, 11), the ITA and the acoustic mode share the same frequency $St = 1/2$. For the modes to coalesce, they need also to have the same growth rate. The acoustic mode is marginally stable. For the ITA mode to also be marginally stable, the gain of the flame response must be $n_{XP} = (1 + \xi)/\theta$. It is straight forward to demonstrate that the eigenvalue $s_{XP}^* = i\pi$ and the set of parameters $(\tau_d^* = 1/2, n_{XP})$ satisfy Eqs. (9, 13).

However, in general, the XP cannot be found analytically, and even finding it numerically remains challenging. For the configuration $\tau_u^* = 0.45$ depicted in Fig. 5, the method introduced by Schaefer et al. [51] is applied to identify the exceptional point. Results are shown in Fig. 6. Colors indicate isolines of flame strength n , along which the downstream propagation time τ_d^* varies. We observe strong mode veering, a manifestation of avoided crossing of two eigenvalues [20, 21, 43, 52]. The presence of the XP induces the eigenvalues to strongly veer, resulting in the characteristic trajectories observed in Fig. 5. This also explains why modes can switch nature, i.e. the mode of acoustic nature when τ_d^* is small becomes ITA for large values of τ_d^* , and vice versa.

4 APPLICATION TO CAN-ANNULAR COMBUSTORS

In this section, we want to extend the model to can-annular configurations. We first describe a typical can-annular combustor. We then show how such system can be reduced to a simple Rijke tube, thus allowing us to transpose the methods and results of Secs. 2 and 3. Finally, we discuss the assumptions and limitations of our modeling approach.

4.1 Case Description and Low-Order Modeling

The generic combustor consists of N identical cans placed in an annular arrangement. Upstream the cans, we neglect the impact of the plenum, as it often shows little influence [33]. The cans are acoustically decoupled and the inlet reflection coefficient is set to $R_i = -1$. At the outlet of the cans, a turbine is placed to extract energy from the fluid. The acoustic response of the turbine stage is modeled by a reflection coefficient with a fixed gain and a

Table 1: Geometrical and thermodynamic parameters of a generic can-annular combustor such as presented in [33]. The FTF parameters are adapted from [53].

	Configuration A	Configuration B
N [-]	10	10
H [m]	0.15	0.15
L_g^* [-]	0.25	0.25
n [-]	1.2	1.2
τ_F [s]	3.5×10^{-3}	3.5×10^{-3}
L_u [m]	0.5	0.8
L_d [m]	1.5	1.2

zero phase response [54], we choose $R_o = 1$ as losses have little quantitative impact [55]. The Mach number is low, typically below 0.2 [27, 29]. Consequently, we assume zero mean flow when modeling the thermoacoustic behavior of the cans. Finally, entropy waves are assumed to have a negligible effect and are not taken into account [29, 56].

Fig. 7 depicts a unit-cell of the investigated can-annular combustor. Following previous studies [29, 35], we consider cans of width H and a gap of size L_g , leading to the coupling strength between cans $L_g^* = L_g/H$. The flame is placed inside the can at a distance L_u and L_d from the inlet and outlet, respectively. Two cases are investigated: Configuration A has a shorter upstream duct than Configuration B, however the total length of the combustor $L_u + L_d$ is kept constant. The modeling of the flame is identical to Sec. 2.2. For the sake of simplicity, we consider a simple $n - \tau$ model adapted from [53], but results could be easily extended to realistic flames, since distributed time delay models are nothing more but a collection of individual $n - \tau$ models [47]. The geometrical and thermodynamic parameters, inspired from a realistic combustor such as presented in [33], are given in Table 1.

4.2 Bloch Theory

As the cans are geometrically identical, the system exhibits discrete rotational symmetry. Applying Bloch theory [57], which is now well established in thermoacoustics [24, 29, 33–35, 58, 59], the acoustic pressure in the frequency domain can be written as:

$$\hat{p}(\mathbf{x}) = \psi(\mathbf{x}) e^{im\varphi}, \quad m = \begin{cases} -\frac{N}{2} + 1, \dots, \frac{N}{2} & N \text{ even} \\ -\frac{N-1}{2}, \dots, \frac{N-1}{2} & N \text{ odd} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Fig. 8: For the considered generic can-annular configuration, the phase response of the gap obtained with FEM Helmholtz computations (full lines) is shown as a function of the dimensionless frequency St . The 1D model based on a characteristic length (crosses) shows perfect agreement with the reference. The phase response of the gap for the axial mode is trivially null. For all other azimuthal orders, starting from π , the phase monotonically decreases towards zero. For low frequencies $St < 1$, the phase response of the gap can be approximated by the tangent at the origin (dashed line). The higher the azimuthal order m , the wider the frequency range over which this approximation holds.

where φ is the azimuthal coordinate around the axis of rotational symmetry, m is the Bloch wave number, identical to the azimuthal order [29] and $\psi(\mathbf{x})$ a function identical in all unit-cells and $2\pi/N$ periodic in φ .

The eigenmodes are classified in three groups: axial or push-push ($m = 0$), push-pull ($m = N/2$) and azimuthal modes (all other values of m). We additionally assume reflection symmetry along the planes $\varphi = \text{const.}$ that pass through the center of the cell (no mean flow in the azimuthal direction): the azimuthal modes come in degenerate pairs which differ only by their spinning direction. From the study of a single unit-cell, the behavior of the full system is preserved by considering all azimuthal mode orders m . We reduce the can-annular system to a single unit-cell and apply Bloch boundaries in the gap region.

4.3 Equivalent Rijke Tube Model

Previous studies [24,33–35] showed the possibility of transforming a can-annular configuration into an equivalent longitudinal combustor, where all the 2D effects of can-to-can communication in the cross-talk area are lumped into an equivalent outlet reflection coefficient \mathcal{R}_m . Using the characteristic length model introduced by Fournier et al. [35],

the equivalent reflection coefficient writes

$$\mathcal{R}_m = 1 - \frac{2 \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi m}{N}\right)}{iSt \frac{\pi L_{char, m}^* \tau_c^*}{L_g^*} + \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi m}{N}\right)} \quad (16)$$

with $L_g^* = L_g/H$ the coupling strength between the cans due to the size of the gap, $L_{char, m}^* = L_{char, m}/H$ the dimensionless characteristic length that models the inertia of the volume of fluid, and $\tau_c^* = H/(c_d \tau_F)$ the dimensionless propagation time in the azimuthal direction. The axial mode is a special case because the equivalent reflection coefficient is simply $\mathcal{R}_{m=0} = 1$: the push-push mode is not affected by the acoustic communication with neighboring cans, i.e. the eigenmode is exactly the same as in the single can system. For all the other azimuthal mode orders, the gain of the equivalent reflection coefficient \mathcal{R}_m is unity, however its phase response is not trivial, as shown in Fig. 8. Starting from π , the phase monotonically decreases and converges towards zero as the frequency increases. The characteristic length model shows perfect agreement with the FEM Helmholtz reference obtained with COMSOL MULTIPHYSICS. For low frequencies $St < 1$, the phase response of the gap can be approximated by the tangent at the origin, indicated by the dashed lines in Fig. 8. Since the phase depends linearly of the frequency St , following the approach of Fournier et al. [24], the equivalent reflection coefficient \mathcal{R}_m can therefore be replaced by a duct of length \mathcal{L}_m terminated by a fully reflecting open end as shown in Fig. 9. This equivalent duct of length \mathcal{L}_m induces an additional propagation time $\tau_m^* = \mathcal{L}_m/(c_d \tau_F)$ downstream of the cans that writes:

$$\mathcal{L}_m = \frac{L_{char, m}^* H}{2L_g^* \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi m}{N}\right)}, \quad \tau_m^* = \frac{L_{char, m}^* \tau_c^*}{2L_g^* \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi m}{N}\right)} \quad (17)$$

For a given geometry, the higher the azimuthal order, the shorter the equivalent duct. The full configuration is, therefore, reduced to a simple Rijke tube, whose downstream length varies with the azimuthal order m , representing the fact that the acoustic response of the gap is mode order dependent. In consequence, the methodology and analysis introduced in Secs. 2 and 3 can be used to understand the spectrum of the can-annular configurations. Note however that this does not apply to the axial mode, which is simply obtained by solving the single can combustor.

4.4 Clusters of Eigenmodes and Their Trajectories

Figs. 10 and 11 show the spectrum of the can-annular combustor of the Configuration A and B, respectively. Following the methodology introduced in Sec. 3, since the upstream condition is, in both cases, fixed, the trajectories

Fig. 9: Equivalent Rijke tube with fully reflecting boundaries. The equivalent length \mathcal{L}_m varies with the azimuthal order of the mode considered and models the behavior of the acoustic communication through the gap. The larger the azimuthal order, the shorter \mathcal{L}_m .

Fig. 10: Eigenvalues of the can-annular Configuration A as predicted by FEM Helmholtz simulations (circles) compared to the equivalent Rijke tube model (crosses). The latter shows excellent agreement with the reference. Colors indicate the azimuthal order as defined in Fig. 8. Except for the axial mode, all the eigenvalues are located on the trajectories obtained when varying τ_d^* . Their position on the trajectory depends on the mode order through the additional equivalent length \mathcal{L}_m . Note that modes $m = 4$ and $m = 5$ almost coincide. The ITA and acoustic clusters are distinct.

when varying the downstream length are obtained. The circles indicate the eigenvalues computed with the reference FEM Helmholtz simulations, while the crosses are the results from the equivalent Rijke tube model described in Sec. 4.3. The latter shows excellent agreement with the reference. A small discrepancy is observed for the first azimuthal order $m = 1$. This is explained by the fact that the approximation of a linear phase response of the gap is valid only for low frequencies, as shown in Fig. 8, and the low azimuthal orders are the first to deviate from this approximation.

For Configuration A, $\tau_u^* = 0.251$ and the trajectories obtained resemble those shown in Fig. 4. For Configuration B, $\tau_u^* = 0.402$ and the trajectories are similar to Fig. 5. In particular, an exceptional point forces the trajectories to veer in order to avoid crossing. It is highlighted that, for both configurations, all the other eigenvalues are located on the trajectories (except for the special case of the axial mode $m = 0$, which behaves differently from the rest of

Fig. 11: Eigenvalues of the can-annular Configuration B as predicted by FEM Helmholtz simulations (circles) compared to the equivalent Rijke tube model (crosses). The latter shows excellent agreement with the reference. Colors indicate the azimuthal order as defined in Fig. 8. All azimuthal eigenmodes are located on the trajectories obtained when varying τ_d^* and their exact position on it depends on the mode order through the additional equivalent length \mathcal{L}_m . Note that modes $m = 4$ and $m = 5$ almost coincide. For this configuration, the presence of an XP make the eigenmodes strongly veer.

the cluster due to its different boundary conditions). Indeed, for all the azimuthal orders, the Rijke tube models are identical, in particular they share the same flame response and upstream conditions. However, they differ by their total downstream propagation times, which is $\tau_t^* = \tau_d^* + \tau_m^*$, where τ_d^* is here a constant fixed by the can length L_d , whereas τ_m^* , due to the effective length \mathcal{L}_m added to model the behavior of the gap, shows an explicit dependence on the azimuthal mode order. This fully explains the presence of all the eigenmodes on these trajectories. Their exact position is, however, determined by the total downstream propagation time τ_t^* . Following Eq. (17), low azimuthal order modes are associated to large values of τ_m^* , leading to larger total downstream propagation time τ_t^* as observed in Figs. 10, 11. In summary, the upstream conditions impose the eigenmodes to follow specific trajectories, while their exact position is fixed by the downstream conditions. This helps us to better understand the spectrum observed initially in Fig. 1. For Configuration A, the clusters are well separated, they do not interplay and can easily be identified. For Configuration B, the presence of an exceptional point plays a decisive role in shaping the trajectories (with a characteristic veer where the modes seem to repel each other), and, consequently, the spectrum of the considered system. Although the clusters seem entangled, we can now easily understand the trajectories the eigenmodes will follow when changing parameters.

This new insight could be exploited for early stage designs of new can-annular engines. Assuming that the

design of the burners is fixed and that the flame response is known for a given amount of operating conditions, it may be possible to investigate the role of the upstream and downstream geometry on the thermoacoustic spectrum. The choice of the upstream can length L_u will impose the trajectories in the complex plane on which the eigenmodes are necessarily located. Finally, choosing the downstream length and the gap parameters will then govern their exact position on these trajectories. Note that changing the downstream parameters affects the system and the modes location in different ways. For example, changing the downstream length L_d induces a change in the total downstream length that is identical for all mode orders: all the modes are translated along the trajectories. Conversely, the impact of a modification in the geometry of the cross-talk area (width of the can or coupling strength) is different for each azimuthal order, since τ_m^* shows an explicit dependence to the mode order as shown in Eq. (17). Note also that changing the size of the gap or the width of the can have antagonist effects. Indeed, the larger the gap, *ceteris paribus*, the smaller the equivalent length, and the closer the eigenvalues along the trajectories. Modes of higher azimuthal order are closest within a cluster. Conversely, increasing the width of the can increases the effective length \mathcal{L}_m , leading to a wider spread of the clusters.

This could be used to develop strategies to stabilize an engine. Note that when we refer in here to variations of L_u and L_d , we do not necessarily mean a drastic change of geometry, which is out of the question for later stages in the design. Instead, we refer to L_u and L_d as parameters indicating the effect of acoustic transport times upstream and downstream of the flame, which may be emulated by tuning the flow circuits belonging to the combustion chamber. For example, in the Configuration A shown in Fig 10, the modes of azimuthal order $m = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and 5 on the lower branch are unstable. Changing the cross-talk area, by either changing the can width or gap size, will have a marginal effect on stabilizing the cluster: \mathcal{L}_m is already very short for the highest azimuthal order and, no matter the cross-talk design, τ_t^* cannot be smaller than $\tau_t^* = \tau_d^* = 0.49$, which would still be unstable. However, reducing the downstream length of the can L_d would translate all eigenmodes along the trajectory (in the direction of smaller τ_t^*) and have a stabilizing effect on the entire cluster. Note however that a change in L_d will also have an impact on the axial modes $m = 0$ and their trajectories should also be considered for a robust design. Similarly, for Configuration B, as shown in Fig. 11, the eigenmodes associated to the azimuthal order $m = 1$ on the lower branch and $m = 4$ and $m = 5$ on the upper branch are unstable. Increasing the can length L_d would translate all the eigenvalues along the trajectories in the direction of higher τ_t^* , thus stabilizing the two unstable modes of the upper branch. However, it will further destabilize the azimuthal mode $m = 1$ and will impact the stability of the axial modes $m = 0$ as well. Conversely, reducing the coupling strength of the gap L_g^* would tend to increase τ_m^* , which would also have a stabilizing effect on the two unstable modes of the upper branch (τ_m^* small for high azimuthal order). Note however the axial modes $m = 0$ would remain unaffected since the cross-talk area with the neighboring cans has no impact on them. The above

analysis is an example of what the present work offers, which could be of help to develop new strategies for designing stable can-annular combustors during early stage studies. For a complete robust design, clusters of harmonics should also be considered as they may be the most unstable modes.

4.5 Modeling Assumptions and Limits of Validity

In this section, we want to put our results in perspective and briefly discuss the main modeling assumptions and the limits of validity of our models. In Sec. 4.3, we showed the possibility to replace the complex-valued reflection coefficient \mathcal{R}_m by an effective duct length \mathcal{L}_m . The main advantage of this approach is to model a complex system - a cross-talk area in can-annular combustor - with a very simple element, i.e. a duct, which gives good insight and helps the fundamental understanding of the underlying physics. As shown in Fig. 8, for higher azimuthal order m , this modeling assumption is valid over a large frequency range, even for frequencies $St > 3$. On the other hand, for lower azimuthal order, in particular for $m = 1$, the range of validity is much narrower, up to $St < 1$ in our case. However, since we assumed a purely reactive coupling, the error made only affects the phase response of the gap. Consequently, as shown in Figs. 10, 11, the eigenmodes obtained with the equivalent Rijke tube models are indeed located on the trajectories, but their exact positions are mispredicted. In conclusion, for understanding or when considering only the clusters associated with the fundamental modes, the equivalent Rijke tube model can be used. However, when considering clusters of harmonics or to ensure quantitatively accurate results, the characteristic length model of Fournier et al. [35] should be preferred.

In Sec. 4.4, we showed that all the eigenmodes (except the special case $m = 0$) necessarily lie on the same trajectory. This result comes from two main assumptions. First of all, the plenum was considered perfectly decoupled. However, if the plenum is taken into account and modeled as a thin annulus [24,60], it will also introduce an equivalent length \mathcal{L}_m at the inlet that changes with the azimuthal order. Consequently, for each azimuthal order, the upstream condition will be different and each eigenmode will follow its own trajectory. The second reason is the fact that the cross-talk area, modeled with a characteristic length model, is purely reactive. For each azimuthal order, the gap introduces a different phase shift, but there is no amplification nor damping. However, recent studies of Pedernana and Noiray [38] and Orchini et al. [39] showed that, when accounting for mean flow effects, the effective coupling impedance exhibit resistive effects. In particular, as shown in Fig. 5 in [39], the magnitude of the equivalent reflection coefficient is mode order dependent, i.e. depending on the azimuthal order considered, the gap will introduce different amplification or damping. This effect causes the mode to follow distinct trajectories. Finally, and more generally, the 1D low-order modeling approach is inherently limited by two factors: the gap needs to be acoustically compact (or its finite extension modeled as in [36]) and only plane waves propagate in the cans, all other modes being cut-off.

These two factors were already discussed by Fournier et al. [35] and will also limit the number of clusters that can be properly captured with a 1D approach.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Starting from the observation that two similar can-annular configurations can lead to drastically different spectra, we investigated the interplay of acoustic and ITA clusters when they are in the same frequency range. To simplify the problem, we first considered a Rijke tube, which is one of the simplest thermoacoustic system and a fair approximation of can-annular combustors [24, 33], and we derived an analytical low-order network model. Buckingham II theorem allowed us to define dimensionless numbers so that the problem remains generally applicable to configuration of arbitrary parameters. We then investigated the interplay between the acoustic and ITA modes. In particular, for a given flame response, the impact on the eigenmodes of the downstream duct length and the flame position inside the system was analyzed.

For short upstream configurations, when increasing the downstream length, the frequency of the acoustic mode decreases whereas the ITA mode converges to a point identified as the eigenvalue of the semi-anechoic system. Conversely, for longer upstream configurations, the eigenmodes follow more peculiar trajectories and can, for example, switch nature, which confirmed previous observations [18, 34, 46]. In particular, the role of exceptional points in the complex plane was highlighted since it causes the eigenvalues to strongly veer, leading to characteristic trajectories.

We then considered two generic can-annular configurations. Using Bloch theory, we exploited the discrete rotational symmetry to reduce the study to a single unit-cell while preserving the dynamics of the full system. We confirmed the possibility to approximate the systems by a simple Rijke tube where the behavior of the gap was simply lumped into an additional effective length. Such modeling allowed to explain the spectra of both systems. In particular, we showed that, in the absence of mean flow, the eigenmodes necessarily follow specific trajectories, imposed by the upstream conditions, and their exact position along the latter is determined by the gap and downstream parameters. We highlighted that, when ITA and acoustic clusters do not interplay, they are well distinct and identifiable, as exemplified in Configuration A (see Fig. 10). However, the presence of an exceptional point in the complex plane strongly influences the trajectories, as already reported by Silva et al. [43] and Mensah et al. [19]. ITA and acoustic clusters can also be entangled, as illustrated in Fig. 11 with Configuration B. New insight is gained when considering the trajectories the modes follow. In that sense, we confirmed the conclusion of Orchini et al. [21] who showed that the interaction between acoustic modes, ITA modes and exceptional points is essential to predict the stability in (can-)annular combustors.

The proposed framework may be of great utility for the design of can-annular combustors. This is exemplified

with the two cases under investigation at the end of Section. 4.4. The assumptions made by the proposed modeling strategy, as well as the limits of validity, are explicitly discussed in Sec. 4.5.

In this study, we considered a perfectly symmetric can-annular configuration. Symmetry breaking, due to, for example, geometrical imperfections, flow asymmetry or nonlinear response of the flames, plays a major role in annular cavities because the degenerate pairs of azimuthal eigenmodes split into two distinct modes [61]. In can-annular configurations, it would double the number of modes in the acoustic and ITA clusters and could potentially affect their trajectories or lead to peculiar behaviors such as mode localization. This effect should be investigated in future studies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 765998 *Annular Instabilities and Transient Phenomena in Gas Turbine Combustors (ANNULIGHT)* and from the Research Association for Combustion Engines (Forschungsvereinigung Verbrennungskraftmaschinen e.V. FVV, project number 6012700). The authors would also like to thank Max Meindl for valuable discussions and his help with FEM COMSOL MULTIPHYSICS simulations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lieuwen, T., and McManus, K., 2003. “Combustion Dynamics in Lean-Premixed Prevaporized (LPP) Gas Turbines”. *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **19**(5), pp. 721–721.
- [2] Poinso, T., 2017. “Prediction and Control of Combustion Instabilities in Real Engines”. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*, **36**, pp. 1–28.
- [3] Lieuwen, T., and Yang, V., eds., 2005. *Combustion Instabilities in Gas Turbine Engines: Operational Experience, Fundamental Mechanisms and Modeling*. No. v. 210 in Progress in Astronautics and Aeronautics. American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Reston, VA.
- [4] Culick, F., 1988. “Combustion instabilities in liquid-fuelled propulsion systems - an overview”. In *Combustion Instabilities in Liquid-Fuelled Propulsion Systems*, Vol. 450, AGARD / NATO.
- [5] Lieuwen, T. C., 2012. *Unsteady Combustor Physics*. Cambridge University Press, New York, N.Y., USA.
- [6] Hoeijmakers, M., Lopez Arteaga, I., Kornilov, V., Nijmeijer, H., and de Goey, P., 2013. “Experimental Investigation of Intrinsic Flame Stability”. In *European Combustion Meeting, ECM2013, Scandinavian-Nordic Section of the Combustion Institute*.
- [7] Hoeijmakers, M., Kornilov, V., Lopez Arteaga, I., de Goey, P., and Nijmeijer, H., 2014. “Intrinsic Instability of Flame-Acoustic Coupling”. *Combustion and Flame*, **161**(11), Nov., pp. 2860–2867.

-
- [8] Silva, C. F., Emmert, T., Jaensch, S., and Polifke, W., 2015. “Numerical Study on Intrinsic Thermoacoustic Instability of a Laminar Premixed Flame”. *Combustion and Flame*, **162**(9), pp. 3370–3378.
- [9] Courtine, E., Selle, L., and Poinso, T., 2015. “DNS of Intrinsic Thermoacoustic Modes in Laminar Premixed Flames”. *Combustion and Flame*, **162**(11), pp. 4331–4341.
- [10] Bomberg, S., Emmert, T., and Polifke, W., 2015. “Thermal Versus Acoustic Response of Velocity Sensitive Premixed Flames”. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*, **35**(3), pp. 3185–3192.
- [11] Emmert, T., Bomberg, S., and Polifke, W., 2015. “Intrinsic Thermoacoustic Instability of Premixed Flames”. *Combustion and Flame*, **162**(1), pp. 75–85.
- [12] Emmert, T., Bomberg, S., Jaensch, S., and Polifke, W., 2017. “Acoustic and Intrinsic Thermoacoustic Modes of a Premixed Combustor”. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*, **36**(3), pp. 3835–3842.
- [13] Yong, K. J., Silva, C. F., and Polifke, W., 2021. “A Categorization of Marginally Stable Thermoacoustic Modes Based on Phasor Diagrams”. *Combustion and Flame*, **228**, pp. 236–249.
- [14] Dowling, A. P., and Stow, S. R., 2003. “Acoustic Analysis of Gas Turbine Combustors”. *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **19**(5), pp. 751–764.
- [15] Eckstein, J., and Sattelmayer, T., 2006. “Low-order modeling of low-frequency combustion instabilities in aeroengines”. *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **22**(2), pp. 425–432.
- [16] Ghani, A., Steinbacher, T., Albayrak, A., and Polifke, W., 2019. “Intrinsic thermoacoustic feedback loop in turbulent spray flames”. *Combustion and Flame*, **205**(7), pp. 22–32.
- [17] Albayrak, A., Steinbacher, T., Komarek, T., and Polifke, W., 2017. “Convective Scaling of Intrinsic Thermoacoustic Eigenfrequencies of a Premixed Swirl Combustor”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **140**(4), Nov., p. 041510.
- [18] Hosseini, N., Kornilov, V., Lopez Arteaga, I., Polifke, W., Teerling, O., and de Goey, L., 2018. “Intrinsic thermoacoustic modes and their interplay with acoustic modes in a Rijke burner”. *International Journal of Spray and Combustion Dynamics*, **10**(4), Dec., pp. 315–325.
- [19] Mensah, G. A., Magri, L., Silva, C. F., Buschmann, P. E., and Moeck, J. P., 2018. “Exceptional points in the thermoacoustic spectrum”. *J. Sound Vibration*, **433**, Oct., pp. 124–128.
- [20] Silva, C., Yong, K. J., and Magri, L., 2019. “Thermoacoustic Modes of Quasi-One-Dimensional Combustors in the Region of Marginal Stability”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **141**(2), Feb., p. 021022.
- [21] Orchini, A., Silva, C. F., Mensah, G. A., and Moeck, J. P., 2020. “Thermoacoustic modes of intrinsic and acoustic origin and their interplay with exceptional points”. *Combustion and Flame*, **211**, pp. 83–95.
- [22] Buschmann, P. E., Mensah, G. A., Nicoud, F., and Moeck, J. P., 2020. “Solution of Thermoacoustic Eigenvalue

-
- Problems With a Noniterative Method”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **142**(3), Mar.
- [23] Buschmann, P. E., Mensah, G. A., and Moeck, J. P., 2020. “Intrinsic thermoacoustic modes in an annular combustion chamber”. *Combustion and Flame*, **214**, Apr., pp. 251–262.
- [24] Fournier, G. J. J., Haeringer, M., Silva, C. F., and Polifke, W., 2021. “Low-Order Modeling to Investigate Clusters of Intrinsic Thermoacoustic Modes in Annular Combustors”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **143**(4), Apr., p. 041025.
- [25] Bethke, S., Krebs, W., Flohr, P., and Prade, B., 2002. “Thermoacoustic properties of can annular combustors”. In 8th AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference & Exhibit, AIAA 2002-2570, p. 2570.
- [26] Kaufmann, P., Krebs, W., Valdes, R., and Wever, U., 2008. “3D Thermoacoustic Properties of Single Can and Multi Can Combustor Configurations”. In Volume 3: Combustion, Fuels and Emissions, Parts A and B, ASMEDC, pp. 527–538.
- [27] Panek, L., Farisco, F., and Huth, M., 2017. “Thermo-Acoustic Characterization of Can-Can Interaction of a Can-Annular Combustion System Based on Unsteady CFD LES Simulation”. In Proc 1st Global Power and Propulsion Forum, GPPF-2017-81, GPPS.
- [28] Farisco, F., Panek, L., and Kok, J. B., 2017. “Thermo-acoustic cross-talk between cans in a can-annular combustor”. *International Journal of Spray and Combustion Dynamics*, **9**(4), Dec., pp. 452–469.
- [29] Ghirardo, G., Di Giovine, C., Moeck, J. P., and Bothien, M. R., 2019. “Thermoacoustics of Can-Annular Combustors”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **141**(1), Jan., p. 011007.
- [30] Jegal, H., Moon, K., Gu, J., Li, L. K., and Kim, K. T., 2019. “Mutual synchronization of two lean-premixed gas turbine combustors: Phase locking and amplitude death”. *Combustion and Flame*, **206**, Aug., pp. 424–437.
- [31] Moon, K., Jegal, H., Gu, J., and Kim, K. T., 2019. “Combustion-acoustic interactions through cross-talk area between adjacent model gas turbine combustors”. *Combustion and Flame*, **202**, Apr., pp. 405–416.
- [32] Moon, K., Jegal, H., Yoon, C., and Kim, K. T., 2020. “Cross-talk-interaction-induced combustion instabilities in a can-annular lean-premixed combustor configuration”. *Combustion and Flame*, **220**, Oct., pp. 178–188.
- [33] Haeringer, M., Fournier, G. J. J., Meindl, M., and Polifke, W., 2021. “A Strategy to Tune Acoustic Terminations of Single-Can Test-Rigs to Mimic Thermoacoustic Behavior of a Full Engine”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **143**(7), July, p. 710029.
- [34] von Saldern, J., Orchini, A., and Moeck, J., 2021. “Analysis of Thermoacoustic Modes in Can-Annular Combustors Using Effective Bloch-Type Boundary Conditions”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **143**(7), July, p. 071019.
- [35] Fournier, G. J. J., Meindl, M., Silva, C. F., Ghirardo, G., Bothien, M. R., and Polifke, W., 2021. “Low-Order

-
- Modeling of Can-Annular Combustors”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **143**(12), Dec., p. 121004.
- [36] von Saldern, J. G. R., Orchini, A., and Moeck, J. P., 2021. “A Non-Compact Effective Impedance Model for Can-to-Can Acoustic Communication: Analysis and Optimization of Damping Mechanisms”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **143**(12), Dec., p. 121024.
- [37] Orchini, A., 2022. “An effective impedance for modelling the aeroacoustic coupling of ducts connected via apertures”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **520**, Mar., p. 116622.
- [38] Pedergnana, T., and Noiray, N., 2022. “Coupling-induced instability in a ring of thermoacoustic oscillators”. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, **478**(2259), Mar., p. 20210851.
- [39] Orchini, A., Pedergnana, T., Buschmann, P. E., Moeck, J. P., and Noiray, N., 2022. “Reduced-order modelling of thermoacoustic instabilities in can-annular combustors”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **526**, May, p. 116808.
- [40] Chu, B.-T., 1953. “On the generation of pressure waves at a plane flame front”. *Symposium (International) on Combustion*, **4**(1), Jan., pp. 603–612.
- [41] Crocco, L., 1951. “Aspects of Combustion Stability in Liquid Propellant Rocket Motors Part1: Fundamentals. Low frequency instability with monopropellants”. *Journal of the American Rocket Society*, **21**(6), pp. 163–178.
- [42] Barenblatt, G. I., 2003. *Scaling*. Cambridge Texts in Applied Mathematics. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- [43] Silva, C. F., and Polifke, W., 2019. “Non-dimensional groups for similarity analysis of thermoacoustic instabilities”. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*, **37**, pp. 5289–5297.
- [44] Emmert, T., Meindl, M., Jaensch, S., and Polifke, W., 2016. “Linear State Space Interconnect Modeling of Acoustic Systems”. *Acta Acustica united with Acustica*, **102**(5), pp. 824–833.
- [45] Mensah, G. A., 2019. “Efficient Computation of Thermoacoustic Modes”. PhD thesis, TU Berlin, Fak. V, Verkehrs- und Maschinensysteme, Berlin.
- [46] Sogaro, F. M., Schmid, P. J., and Morgans, A. S., 2019. “Thermoacoustic interplay between intrinsic thermoacoustic and acoustic modes: Non-normality and high sensitivities”. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, **878**, pp. 190–220.
- [47] Polifke, W., 2020. “Modeling and Analysis of Premixed Flame Dynamics by Means of Distributed Time Delays”. *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.*, **79**, p. 100845.
- [48] Æsøy, E., Nygård, H. T., Worth, N. A., and Dawson, J. R., 2022. “Tailoring the gain and phase of the flame transfer function through targeted convective-acoustic interference”. *Combustion and Flame*, **236**, Feb., p. 111813.

-
- [49] Yong, K. J., Silva, C. F., Fournier, G. J. J., and Polifke, W., 2022. “Categorization of Thermoacoustic Modes in an Ideal Resonator with Phasor Diagrams”. *submitted to Combustion and Flame*.
- [50] Mukherjee, N. K., and Shriram, V., 2017. “Intrinsic Flame Instabilities in Combustors: Analytic Description of a 1-D Resonator Model”. *Combustion and Flame*, **185**, pp. 188–209.
- [51] Schaefer, F., Guo, S., and Polifke, W., 2020. “The Impact of Exceptional Points on the Reliability of Thermoacoustic Stability Analysis”. *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power*.
- [52] Sogaro, F., Schmid, P., and Morgans, A. S., 2017. “Sensitivity Analysis of Thermoacoustic Instabilities”. In 2 Int. Conf. on Sound and Vibration, IIAV.
- [53] Tay-Wo-Chong, L., Bomberg, S., Ulhaq, A., Komarek, T., and Polifke, W., 2012. “Comparative Validation Study on Identification of Premixed Flame Transfer Function”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **134**(2), pp. 021502–1–8.
- [54] Marble, F. E., and Candel, S. M., 1977. “Acoustic Disturbance from Gas Non-Uniformities Convected Through a Nozzle”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **55**(2), Nov., pp. 225–243.
- [55] Bauerheim, M., Duran, I., Livebardon, T., Wang, G., Moreau, S., and Poinso, T., 2016. “Transmission and reflection of acoustic and entropy waves through a stator–rotor stage”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **374**, pp. 260–278.
- [56] Morgans, A. S., and Duran, I., 2016. “Entropy Noise: A Review of Theory, Progress and Challenges”. *International Journal of Spray and Combustion Dynamics*, **8**(4), pp. 285–298.
- [57] Bloch, F., 1929. “Über die Quantenmechanik der Elektronen in Kristallgittern”. *Zeitschrift für Physik*, **52**(7-8), July, pp. 555–600.
- [58] Mensah, G. A., Campa, G., and Moeck, J. P., 2016. “Efficient Computation of Thermoacoustic Modes in Industrial Annular Combustion Chambers Based on Bloch-Wave Theory”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **138**(8), Aug., p. 081502.
- [59] Ghirardo, G., Moeck, J. P., and Bothien, M. R., 2020. “Effect of Noise and Nonlinearities on Thermoacoustics of Can-Annular Combustors”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **142**(4), Apr., p. 041005.
- [60] Bauerheim, M., Parmentier, J.-F., Salas, P., Nicoud, F., and Poinso, T., 2014. “An analytical model for azimuthal thermoacoustic modes in an annular chamber fed by an annular plenum”. *Combustion and Flame*, **161**(5), May, pp. 1374–1389.
- [61] Bauerheim, M., Salas, P., Nicoud, F., and Poinso, T., 2014. “Symmetry breaking of azimuthal thermo-acoustic modes in annular cavities: A theoretical study”. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, **760**, Dec., pp. 431–465.